

Musaqah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics around the Musaqaah agreement on Islamic Financial Inclusion using a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Musaqaah " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around the Musaqaah contract based on the journals that have been collected. The results of the research show that there are 4 mapping research topics around the Musaqaah contract, including: the differences between the Musaqaah, Muzara'ah and Mudharabah contracts, the influence of the Musaqaah contract on achieving food self-sufficiency, the application of the Musaqaah contract in the agricultural and plantation sectors, and the influence of the Musaqaah contract on welfare. farm workers. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics surrounding the Musaqaah contract, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Musaqaah; Islamic Financial Inclusion; Library Research

Introduction

One of the important sectors in life is the agricultural sector. Agricultural activities are one of the supporting factors in meeting people's living needs. Agricultural management is usually carried out individually (by themselves) or managed by other people who work on the land. In fulfilling the needs of the community, besides that, there is community welfare so that cooperation occurs. This collaboration is linked to the management of agricultural land between land owners and cultivators. Cooperation in the plantation sector has been widely carried out in Indonesia, which is an agricultural country. Cooperation recommended in Islam uses a profit sharing system. Where sharecroppers and plantation owners share the results after harvesting the agricultural products they work on. The Musaqaah contract is a collaboration between the garden owner and the poor farmer whose aim is to care for and maintain the garden so that it produces maximum results.

of this research is to map research topics around the Musaqaah agreement using Islamic Financial Inclusion library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding the Musaqaah contract, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this

research is mapping research topics surrounding the Musaqah contract, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Etymologically, musaqah comes from the Arabic word " saqa " which means to flow. Meanwhile, in fiqh, Musaqah is a contractual term for work related to trees, some of which are produced from the harvest. Musaqah means handing over plants to someone who will manage them until harvest by providing certain rewards from the results of the plants. The terms of the Musaqah contract are that both parties must be mumayyiz and sensible, the object of the contract is a plant that bears fruit, and joint ownership of the results obtained.

Islamic Financial Inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit riba (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Islamic Financial Inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of Islamic Financial Inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Islamic Financial Inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, Islamic Financial Inclusion also supports the development of the sharia financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies, and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of literature study research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, literature study research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and compile the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Methodology

This research uses a qualitative approach in the nature of a library research. The object of the research is the Musaqah contract. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about Musaqah contracts in Islamic Financial Inclusion. The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Musaqah " within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data

in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around the Musaqah contract based on the journals that have been collected.

Results and Discussion

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Differences between Musaqah, Muzara'ah and Mudharabah Contracts

library research study in previous research journals, researchers found differences between Musaqah, Muzara'ah and Mudharabah contracts. The main difference between these three contracts lies in the nature of cooperation and the division of roles between the parties involved. Musaqah and muzara'ah are related to agriculture, where musaqah does not involve the provision of capital by the land owner, while muzara'ah involves the provision of capital by the land manager. On the other hand, mudharabah relates to business or finance, where capital is provided by the owner of the capital, and the manager is responsible for the business and its management.

Here is a brief explanation of the differences between them:

1. Musaqah. Musaqah is a cooperation agreement in the agricultural sector. In a musaqah contract, one party as the land owner (musaqi) agrees to an agreement with another party (saqi) who will manage the land. The saqi will be responsible for planting, caring for and maintaining the plants on the land. The harvest will be divided between musaqui and saqi according to a previously determined agreement. Musaqah does not involve the provision of capital by the musaqi.
2. Muzara'ah. Muzara'ah is also a form of cooperation in the agricultural sector. In a muzara'ah contract, the land owner (muzara') and another party (zari') who acts as the land manager agree to share the harvest. However, the difference with musaqah is that in muzara'ah, the zari' will provide some of the capital such as seeds, fertilizer and agricultural equipment. After harvest, the results will be divided between muzara' and zari' according to previously agreed agreements.
3. Mudharabah. Mudharabah is a form of cooperation in the business or financial sector. In a mudharabah contract, one party as the owner of capital (shahibul maal) agrees to an agreement with another party as the manager (mudharib) who will use the capital to conduct business. The profits generated will be shared between the shahibul maal and the mudharib according to a previously determined agreement, while losses are usually borne by the shahibul maal. In mudharabah, capital is provided by shahibul maal, while mudharib provides expertise and effort to run the business.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Influence of the Musaqah Agreement on Achieving Food Self-Sufficiency

library research study in previous research journals, researchers found the influence of the Musaqah contract in achieving food self-sufficiency, including:

1. Optimizing land use: By using a musaqah contract, land that is not used optimally can be cultivated by agricultural entrepreneurs who have

knowledge and skills in agriculture. This can increase productivity and the potential of the land to produce more food products.

2. Providing labor: Through musaqah contracts, agricultural entrepreneurs can provide skilled and trained labor to manage agricultural land. With adequate labor, the cultivation, maintenance and harvest processes can be carried out efficiently, so that the potential for food production increases.
3. Risk sharing: In a musaqah contract, risks related to agricultural production can be shared between the land owner and the agricultural entrepreneur. This provides certainty to land owners that they will get some of the production, even though there is a risk of crop failure or other factors affecting production. This risk sharing can encourage landowners to be more willing to give up their land for agricultural activities.
4. Improved agricultural technology: In order to achieve food self-sufficiency, the use of modern and efficient agricultural technology is very important. Through musaqah contracts, agricultural entrepreneurs can apply the latest agricultural technology in land management, such as better irrigation, use of appropriate fertilizer, or more effective pest control. This can increase productivity and quality of harvest.
5. Transfer of knowledge and skills: Musaqah contracts allow for the transfer of knowledge and skills between land owners and agricultural entrepreneurs. Experienced agricultural entrepreneurs can share their knowledge in terms of cultivation, farm management or selecting optimal crop varieties. This can improve landowners' ability to manage their own land in the future.

Research Topic Mapping using Library Research regarding the Implementation of the Musaqah Agreement in the Agriculture and Plantation Sector

library research study in previous research journals, researchers found the application of the Musaqah contract in the agricultural and plantation sectors. The following are general steps in implementing the Musaqah agreement in these two sectors:

1. Land identification: The land owner determines the area of land that will be rented to entrepreneurs for cultivation.
2. Agreement: The land owner and musaqi make a contractual agreement that includes detailed terms and agreed revenue sharing. This agreement can include the duration of the rental, the types of plants to be planted, the maintenance that must be carried out, and the distribution of profits that will be obtained.
3. Plant management: Musaqi is responsible for managing the plants on the land, including soil preparation, planting, fertilizing, watering and maintaining the plants in accordance with the agreement that has been made.
4. Financing: Land owners can provide musaqi with the initial capital required for crop management. This capital can be in the form of cash, plant seeds, fertilizer, or agricultural equipment. The amount of capital and the method of return must be specified in the agreement.
5. Profit sharing: After harvest, the production will be divided between the land owner and the musaqi according to the initial agreement. This profit sharing can be a fixed percentage, a distribution based on capital or labor contributions, or a combination of both.

6. End of contract: After the lease period ends, the land owner and musaqi can decide to extend the contract or terminate the collaboration. If the contract is extended, the previous steps can be repeated.

Research Topic Mapping using Library Research regarding the Influence of the Musaqah Agreement on the Welfare of Farm Workers

library research study in previous research journals, researchers found the influence of the Musaqah agreement on the welfare of farm workers. This may vary depending on implementation and existing socio-economic conditions. The following are several possible influences of the Musaqah agreement on the welfare of farm workers:

1. Access to resources: In Musaqah contracts, farmworkers can access land that they may not personally own. This allows them to engage in agricultural activities and utilize productive resources that were previously unavailable to them. Thus, the Musaqah contract can increase their access to resources and income potential.
2. Risk sharing: In the Musaqah contract, the land or capital owner shares the risk with the farm worker. If the harvest is bad, the owner of the land or capital will also get a smaller share or even no profit. This can provide protection against the economic risks faced by agricultural workers, thereby increasing the stability of their income.
3. Skills and training: Through the Musaqah agreement, agricultural workers can receive training and guidance from land or capital owners who have knowledge and experience in agriculture. This can improve the skills and knowledge of farm workers, so that they can increase productivity and efficiency in agricultural activities.
4. Increased income: If the harvest is successful, farm workers will get a share of the profits according to the agreement in the Musaqah contract. If agricultural production increases, farm laborers' income can also increase. This can have a positive impact on their well-being and improve their standard of living and ability to meet basic needs.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 4 research topic mappings using literature studies regarding Musaqah contracts in Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely: (1) Differences between Musaqah, Muzara'ah and Mudharabah contracts; (2) The influence of the Musaqah agreement on achieving food self-sufficiency; (3) Implementation of the Musaqah contract in the agricultural and plantation sectors; and (4) The influence of the Musaqah agreement on the welfare of farm workers.

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